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Abstract	The work performed with this specific task are to establish a holistic overview of the different technologies contributing to the overall Persephone vision and objectives. The work has been aligned with WP and task leaders and followed up on WP leader sync meetings. Based on the initial proof of concepts the conclusion is that the project is prepared for the upcoming 18 months of project implementation.

History of Changes

Version	Date	Reason of change
0.1	250430	First draft
0.2	250601	Updates from task leaders
1.0	250624	Final version with additional input from WP and task leaders

Executive summary

Within the frame of this specific task, **5 Mission Scenarios** for the PERSEPHONE project have been detailed out in a general project integration checklist. All associated work packages, tasks, objectives, novelties, and deliverables have been listed and detailed for serving as a base for the integration work within the project.

The checklist is mainly used for two purposes:

The first purpose is to track the progress of the technical work and achievements of the project with respect to integration efforts; but also, to identify other noteworthy achievements and results.

The second purpose is to enable WP10 to streamline communication and dissemination by providing a coherent narrative that all WPs, tasks, and results can be related to. The document and the Mission Objectives will also serve as management tool for WP8 and for the project as a whole.

The work has continuously been reviewed in the WP synchronization meeting as a tool for integration activities. Having an overview of all interconnections within the project is a powerful tool for monitoring progress.

The conclusion is that the project is aligned with the demands stated in the DoA and prepared for the second and final phase in the project.

Table of content

Table of content	3
1 Abbreviations.....	4
2 Introduction.....	5
2.1 Purpose and scope of the document	5
2.2 Related documents	5
3 Technical Details (Integration progress and Technology maturity assesment)	6
3.1 Methodology.....	6
3.2 Outcome.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
3.2.1 Mission Scenario 1 - Autonomous Mapping.....	8
3.2.2 Mission Scenario 2 – Advance Exploration.....	10
3.2.3 Mission Scenario 3 – Autonomous Production Drilling	13
3.2.4 Mission Scenario 4 - Dynamic geomodelling	15
3.2.5 Mission Scenario 5 – Decision support.....	16
3.3 Validation Infrastructure: Simulation and Field facilities.....	18
3.3.1 Simulation facilities.....	18
3.3.2 Field facilities.....	19
3.4 Validation Activity Across Work Packages.....	22
3.5 Mission scenario status alignment.....	27
4 Future plans.....	29
5 Conclusions	30
6 Annex.....	31

1 Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
CRIRSCO	Committee for Mineral Reserves International Reporting Standards
CUP	KGHM Cuprum
DTU	Technical University of Denmark
EPI	Epiroc
ERT	Electrical Resistivity Tomography
FEM	Finite Element Method
GA	Grant Agreement
GM	Grecian Magnesite
GSB	Polish Geological Institute
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIBS	Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy
LTU	Luleå University of Technology
MRP	MineRP
MWD	Measurement While Drilling
POC	Proof of Concept
ROS	Robot Operating System
SDF	Simulation Description Format
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SoA	State of the Art
SPE	Spectral Industries
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UNFC	United Nations Framework Classification for Resources
UNRMS	United Nations Resource Management System
UPAT	University of Patras
URDF	Unified Robot Description Format
VLM	Vision-Language Model

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope of the document

The objective of this specific Task 8.1 (System integration for realizing the next generation deep exploration drilling machines) is to create an overview including a general follow up tool for the integration activities related to the novel technologies developed within the work packages WP2, WP4, WP6 and upcoming WP7. This has been achieved by creating an integration checklist in relation to the stated project objectives, novelties and deliverables.

The following report summarizes the work performed, achievements and how this was reviewed during the first part of the project implementation phase. This work will set the baseline for the upcoming work within Wp9 and the final part of the PERSEPHONE project

2.2 Related documents

WP1:

Baseline as stated in WP1, covering specifications and requirements for enabling sustainable deep mining.

Related deliveries:

- *D1.1* – Literature survey on SoA technologies and existing roadmaps in the mining industry.
- *D1.2* – Requirements, specifications and benchmarking tools for proposed technologies.

WP2, WP4, WP6:

The input is based on the continuous work within WP2, WP4, WP6 and included deliverables. Also including the baseline created or the upcoming work within the frame of WP7.

Annex 1 part B and A.

3 Integration progress and Technology maturity assessment

3.1 Methodology

The overall concept and vision of PERSEPHONE is illustrated in Figure1. This vision will be achieved by reducing the size of mining machines currently adapted to the human scale and embedding autonomy for risk-aware navigation and full digitalization of the extraction process by digital twin creation and key enabling technologies validation at TRL 5.

The project introduces completely novel approaches in online near mine exploration and overall integration of related data analytics to the mine expansion. It also enables the green transition by reducing the cost and mineral waste generated from deep-mining operations and enables the vision of zero human presence in possible hazardous areas.

Figure 1: Concept & Vision of Persephone project

The overall goal is to digitalize and automate extraction value chain by creating new concepts of energy-efficient autonomous drilling machines with advanced perception capabilities for navigation, face drilling, and core extraction, which will enable data-driven digital twin. See illustration in figure 2 and the work to be detailed out in each related WP.

Figure 2: Sensor input for digital twin creation

The project progress results will be monitored and quantified according to a set of dedicated KPIs, and main conclusions and achievements will be gathered within WP8 and the following WP9 to ensure the replication of the project results and enable the evolution of new data driven business concepts. To this end, within this WP the project envisions the creation of a network and relationships between vendors, suppliers and the global mining industry to study modern business relationships. These activities will be gathered and shared with other relevant initiatives and stakeholders. These activities will be completed by a coherent exploitation strategy and dissemination plan, which will be part of WP10 and WP11 responsibilities.

To safeguard a successful project implementation according to the stated vision and overall objectives integration activities and surveillance is necessary. As a work tool for this, a decision was taken to establish a checklist within excel for a holistic overview of the Persephone concept system and developed novel technologies within the related WP2, WP4, WP6, and WP7 (currently ongoing core technical WPs), which then extends to integrate the upcoming WPs in the second half of the project execution (M18–M36).

This checklist covers and builds on the steps described in the following section. The associated WP's and related tasks are added into this checklist based on where they are contributing as an enabler for the stated vision scenarios.

1: Future Vision of the PERSEPHONE Project

- PERSEPHONE Exploration and Mining suite
- PERSEPHONE investors suite

2: Mission Scenarios

Mission scenarios are created based on the future vision of the PERSEPHONE project and are in full symphony with its objectives and key exploitable technologies:

1. Autonomous Mapping
2. Advance Exploration
3. Autonomous Production Drilling
4. Dynamic Geomodelling
5. Decision support

3: Proof of Concept of Enabling Technology TRL<=5 in support of Vision and mission

To support the future Vision and mission scenarios the different related WP's and included tasks are listed and added into the matrix. The related tasks are added to the matrix based on where they contribute to the different mission scenarios.

4: Proposed Novelties and contribution to Specific Objectives

Based on the mission scenarios the specific objectives are listed in relation to the proposed novelties. This creates an overview that all objectives are covered according to the GA.

5: Technology integration plan and PoC achievements

As a management tool according to the overall objectives of this specific task 8.1, the achievements and PoC are listed in the matrix.

This is in general terms, and to be more described in detail in the related deliverables for each WP.

3.2 Results

The following section describes the details for each stated mission scenario and how the listed related specific WP's and task are contributing accordingly. It's based on checklist information with the intention as earlier described to get a holistic overview instead of adding the excel file into this document. This since it's too large to get an easy overview. The result is describing the achievement and proof of concepts activities during the first 18 months of the project in overall terms. Additional details are described in the related deliverable to each respective WP.

3.2.1 Mission Scenario 1 - Autonomous Mapping

Mission description:

An Autonomous future Underground Mining Machine performs general surveying mission in an unknown tunnel environment without access to communication network or any other infrastructure ("Abandoned Mine").

Expected Outcome of the mission:

By performing this mission, a detailed geometrical 3D virtual mine map is created where potential mineralization's are highlighted.

Work packages and task contributions as enabler for a successful mission.

- *Task 1.3* - End-user requirements for exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines (M1-M5) Lead: GM; Contributors: All
- *Task 4.1* - Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination (M5-M18) Lead: LTU; Contributors: MRP, EPI, DTU, UPAT
- *Task 4.3* - On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment (M12-M18) Lead: LTU; Contributors: EPI, UPAT
- *Task 4.4* - Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure-free mapping and localization (M9-M18) Lead: LTU; Contributors: EPI, MRP, UPAT
- *Task 6.2* -Real-time Detection of Rock Mechanical and Geophysical Properties from Exploration and Extraction Machinery (MWD) (M5-M22) Lead: SPE Contributors: LTU, KGHM, GSB, GM

Contribution to the Specific Objectives and proposed Novelties.

With successful technical implementation this work will be an enabler to the following Specific Objective and Proposed Novelties.

Specific Objectives

- *S01*, Development of independent and autonomous near-mine exploration & extraction mining machines.
- *S04*, Enable online, in-situ analytics technologies for ore-grading while drilling.
- *S05*, PERSEPHONE concept validation in deep and abandoned mines.

Novelties:

- *NO2*, Green and sustainable drilling rigs
- *NO5*, Core analysis and novel sensors

Results & Achievements according Technology Integration and PoC achievements

Results of the work performed during the first reporting period are summarized in the integration and proof of concepts sections. It's a short headline description of the achievements and are detailed out in each specific deliverable per WP.

WP4:

Single and multi-machine mapping scenario achieved. PERSEPHONE machine, equipped with sensor package for autonomous navigation [D4.1] and related

software stack successfully performs an exploration mission of the abandoned mine. During the mission machine selects risk-aware paths based on the traversability assessment [D4.3]. Multi-machine navigation successfully demonstrated complete surveying mission in infrastructure-less scenario with no communication [D4.1] and produces 3D map of the abandoned mine [D4.4]. Multi-spectral camera hardware and software integrated with testing robotic carrier successfully detected mineralization areas.

WP6:

Two manual missions completed at GM and KGHM with Multi-spectral camera (GSB)

Two standalone measurement campaigns have been conducted both at KGHM and GM sites to test a prototype multispectral camera for mineralogical characterization of mine faces. The first test provided valuable inputs for improvements to the design. These improvements have been reflected in the second campaign that shows early, promising results [D6.1].

Conclusions for Mission Scenario nr1:

The initial PoC gives a good base for continuous integration and testing. It also aligns with the overall Persephone vision and mission.

3.2.2 Mission Scenario 2 – Advance Exploration

Mission Description:

Autonomous Underground Mining Machine equipped with drilling capabilities performs targeted exploration drilling mission at pre-defined areas in known tunnel environment without access to communication network ("Near Mine Exploration" / "Info Drilling")

Expected outcome of the mission:

Rock mechanical and chemical information acquired from exploration drilling at exact locations via core-less coring technology at predefined areas that a-priori indicated presence of possible mineralization's (increase confidence in ore grade & geological continuity).

Work packages and task contribution to a successful mission.

- *Task 1.3* - End-user requirements for exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines
- *Task 2.2* - Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems (M5-M18) Lead: DTU; Contributors: EPI, CUP, KGHM, LTU
- *Task 2.4* - Real-time rock characterization as input to systems for sustainable underground mining (M5-M18) Lead: EPI; Contributors: MRP, LTU, GSB, SPE, CUP

- *Task 4.1* - Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination (M5-M18) Lead: LTU; Contributors: MRP, EPI, DTU, UPAT
- *Task 4.2* - High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations (M7-M18)
Lead: LTU; Contributors: EPI, UPAT
- *Task 4.3* - On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment (M12-M18) Lead: LTU; Contributors: EPI, UPAT
- *Task 4.5* - Autonomous Drill Planning and Execution from Onboard Sensing of the Rock Face Characteristics (M6-M18) Lead: DTU; Contributors: EPI, LTU, MRP, KGHM, UPAT
- *Task 6.1* - Advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling using machines based on LIBS and multi spectral sensors (M5-M22) Lead: SPE; Contributors: LTU, GSB, GM
- *Task 6.2* - Real-time Detection of Rock Mechanical and Geophysical Properties from Exploration and Extraction Machinery (MWD) (M5-M22) Lead: SPE; Contributors: LTU, KGHM, GSB, GM

Contribution to the Specific Objectives and proposed Novelties.

The stated related tasks contributing to the following Specific Objective and proposed novelties.

- *S01*, Development of independent and autonomous near-mine exploration & extraction mining machines.
- *S02*: Enable efficient and accurate autonomous near-mine exploration and extraction of mineralization.
- *S04*, Enable online, in-situ analytics technologies for ore-grading while drilling.
- *S05*, PERSEPHONE concept validation in deep and abandoned mines.

Novelties:

- NO1 Next generation autonomous drilling systems
- NO2 Green and sustainable drilling rigs
- NO3 GNC and coordination of autonomous mining machines throughout the near-mine exploration & exploitation operations.
- NO5 Core analysis and novel sensors

Results/Achievements according Technology Integration and PoC achievements

Work performed during the first reporting period results is summarized in the integration and proof of concepts sections. It's a short headline description and are detailed out in each specific deliverable per WP.

WP2:

T2.2 A simulation environment and initial simulation scenarios of robot (Stinger) concept is created.

Concept of a "stinger robot designed and prototyped is developed and build.

T2.4 Test for input and calibration of some MWD is performed. Rock hardness measurements tool tested and verified in real mining conditions.

WP4:

On successfully accomplishing scenario 1, PERSEPHONE machine successfully performs autonomous navigation mission to the identified mineralization areas [D4.1]. On reaching the targeted area, it performs autonomous alignment with the face [D4.2], performs autonomous drill planning and execution based on the onboard sensors [D4.5].

WP6:

Two manual missions completed at GM and KGHM with Multi-spectral camera (GSB) Development and order of acoustic sensor for upcoming testing.

LIBS drilling fluid analyser

Initial tests using a GSB-developed prototype have proven the feasibility of LIBS on brines and slurries during this project. Based on this early prototype, SPE has started the development of a new design using similar principles. The new prototype has many improvements over the old system mostly in terms of handling, size, and adaptability [D6.1].

Multispectral down-hole camera

During the project the idea was conceived to develop a downhole multispectral sensor to study mineralogy behind the mine-face after a hole has been drilled. While not pursued further at the point of writing, a conceptual design has been worked on by GSB and EPI [6.1].

Conclusion Mission Scenario nr2:

The initial PoC gives a good base for continuous integration and testing. It also aligns with the overall Persephone vision and mission.

3.2.3 Mission Scenario 3 – Autonomous Production Drilling

Mission Description:

Autonomous underground mining machine equipped with drilling capabilities performs energy efficient production drilling at a predefined location in a known environment in the presence of other machines with or without access to communication network.

Expected outcome of the mission:

Geometrically well-defined drill holes (prediction of fraction size) visible the mine map with associated rock mechanical and chemical information acquired via core-less coring technology at a mining face.

Work packages and task contribution to a successful mission.

- *Task 1.2. End-user requirements for exploration and extraction of deep and hard to reach deposits (M1-M5) Lead: MRP; Contributors: All*
- *Task 2.1. Rock Mass Preconditioning for reducing energy consumption of extractive processes (M5-M18) Lead: EPI; Contributors: LTU, KGHM, CUP*
- *Task 2.3 - Hole deviation monitoring system for long hole drilling as a blasting quality indicator (M5-M18) Lead: EPI; Contributors: LTU, MRP, CUP, KGHM*
- *Task 2.4 - Real-time rock characterization as input to systems for sustainable underground mining (M5-M18) Lead: EPI; Contributors: MRP, LTU, GSB, SPE, CUP*
- *Task 4.1 - Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination (M5-M18) Lead: LTU; Contributors: MRP, EPI, DTU, UPAT*
- *Task 4.2 - High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations (M7-M18) Lead: LTU; Contributors: EPI, UPAT*
- *Task 4.3 - On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment (M12-M18) Lead: LTU; Contributors: EPI, UPAT*
- *Task 4.4 - Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure-free mapping and localization (M9-M18) Lead: LTU; Contributors: EPI, MRP, UPAT*
- *Task 4.5 - Autonomous Drill Planning and Execution from Onboard Sensing of the Rock Face Characteristics (M6-M18) Lead: DTU; Contributors: EPI, LTU, MRP, KGHM, UPAT*
- *Task 6.1 - Advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling using machines based*

on LIBS and multi spectral sensors (M5-M22) Lead: SPE; Contributors: LTU, GSB, GM

- *Task 6.2* - Real-time Detection of Rock Mechanical and Geophysical Properties from Exploration and Extraction Machinery (MWD) (M5-M22) Lead: SPE; Contributors: LTU, KGHM, GSB, GM

Contribution to the Specific Objectives and proposed Novelties.

The stated related tasks contributing to the following Specific Objective and proposed novelties.

- *SO1*, Development of independent and autonomous near-mine exploration & extraction mining machines.
- *SO2*: Enable efficient and accurate autonomous near-mine exploration and extraction of mineralization.
- *SO4*, Enable online, in-situ analytics technologies for ore-grading while drilling.
- *SO5*, PERSEPHONE concept validation in deep and abandoned mines.

Novelties:

- NO1 Next generation autonomous drilling systems
- NO2 Green and sustainable drilling rigs
- NO3 GNC and coordination of autonomous mining machines throughout the near-mine exploration & exploitation operations.
- NO5 Core analysis and novel sensors

Results/Achievements according Technology Integration and PoC achievements

Work performed during the first reporting period results is summarized in the integration and proof of concepts sections. It's a short headline description and are detailed out in each specific deliverable per WP.

WP2:

T2.1 Simulation environment created, and real blasting performed in KGHM mine to evaluate the effect of pre-conditioning.

T2.3. Hole deviation measurements are performed with probe in real mining environments. Data collected and interface created for transferring of data to the MRP planning system to be developed within WP7

WP4:

On successful accomplishment of the scenarios 1 and 2, the drilling robot in an autonomous mission [D4.1, D4.3, D4.4] performs navigation to the production drilling area identified in scenario 2. On reaching the area high-accuracy alignment [D4.2] and drill planning and execution [D4.5] are performed.

WP6:

Libs slurry analysis performed.

Acoustics and ERT

First lab systems for the development of acoustic and ERT sensing have been constructed. The starting TRL of these technologies is low, so development is still more fundamental. Nonetheless, initial lab results are encouraging and justify further development.

Conclusion Mission Scenario nr3:

The initial PoC gives a good base for continuous integration and testing. It also aligns with the overall Persephone vision and mission.

3.2.4 Mission Scenario 4 - Dynamic geomodelling

Mission description:

Georeferenced information about the deposit is updated to a digital twin accessible for data driven geomodelling. The model is continuously updated with current data when it becomes available.

Expected Outcome of the mission:

An updated Digital twin of the ore deposit is continuously available for a multitude of users from different disciplines and respective outcomes.

Work packages and task contribution to a successful mission.

- *Task 1.6* - Data requirements for geo-models' development (M1-M5) Lead: LTU; Contributors: MRP, GM, GSB
- *Task 2.5* - Computer-aided planning of excavation in exceptional deposit conditions (M5-M18) Lead: CUP; Contributors', MRP

Contribution to the Specific Objectives and proposed Novelties.

The stated related tasks contributing to the following Specific Objective and proposed novelties.

- *S03: Dynamic digital twin-based dynamic and interoperable geo-models for optimal planning of face drilling and extraction*

Novelties:

- NO4 Geo-modelling and online digital twin
- NO6 Downstream integration

Results/Achievements according Technology Integration and PoC achievements

WP1:

T1.6 - Data requirements for geo-models' development (M1-M5) Lead: LTU.

The data requirements essential for the development of dynamic geo-models, along with integration frameworks and quality standards aligned with digital twin and UNFC classification needs, were defined and documented in D1.2. It also outlines data generation plans to support technology development in WP6.

WP2:

T2.5 – preparation of large, three-dimensional numerical models based on the finite element method (FEM), which were calibrated on the basis of actual convergence measurements and geological data from the Rudna mine (KGHM Polska Miedź S.A.). The results clearly confirm the high value of using numerical simulations as a tool for optimizing exploitation strategies and managing geotechnical risk.

Conclusion Mission Scenario nr4:

The initial PoC gives a good base for continuous integration and testing. It also aligns with the overall Persephone vision and mission.

3.2.5 Mission Scenario 5 – Decision support

Mission Description:

Information stored in the digital twin is made available to support different consumption patterns, ranging from operational to strategic decision-making. The digital twin will enable closer to real-time reporting according to CRIRSCO-requirements (for investors) and resource and reserve classification according to UNFC (strategic decision-making for governments and at EU level).

Expected Outcome of the mission:

All relevant players can access the same information from one data source. Information can be tailored to inform investment decisions, production planning, operations, and regulatory compliance reporting.

Work packages and task contributions to a successful mission.

- *Task 1.4* Setting the framework conditions for alignment with the UNFC and UNRMS(M1-M5) Lead: INTRAW; Contributors: All

Contributions to the Specific Objectives and proposed Novelties.

The stated related tasks contributed to the following Specific Objective and proposed novelties.

- *S03: Dynamic digital twin-based dynamic and interoperable geo-models for optimal planning of face drilling and extraction*

Novelties:

- NO4 Geo-modelling and online digital twin
- NO6 Downstream integration

Results/Achievements according Technology Integration and PoC achievements

Results of work performed during the first reporting period are summarized in the integration and proof of concepts (PoC) sections. This is a short summary description, and more details are provided in the respective WP deliverables.

WP1:

Task 1.4 Setting the framework conditions for alignment with the UNFC and UNRMS(M1-M5) Lead: INTRAW; Contributors: All

The Figure nr3 below illustrates the initial conceptual data flow from data acquired in the mine to CRIRSCO-compliant reporting and UNFC classification.

Figure 3: From Geological Data Acquisition to UNFC-Classification (INTRAW)

The decision whether to extract or not and the further routing of any extracted materials in the value-web is illustrated in the flow-chart below.

Figure 4: : Conceptual decision tree for the destination of different types of extracted materials (INTRAW).

These are currently conceptual models and will be further refined in the course of Task 7.1, to be reported in D7.1 at M25.

Conclusion Mission Scenario no. 5:

The initial work a gives a good base for continuous work within the frame of WP7

3.3 Validation Infrastructure: Simulation and Field facilities

To support the iterative development, integration, and validation of technologies across WPs 2–7, the PERSEPHONE project utilizes a combination of advanced simulation environments and real-world mining sites. These infrastructures enable component testing, system-level evaluation, and realistic scenario execution in alignment with the project's five mission scenarios.

3.3.1 Simulation facilities

Simulation tools play a critical role for early-stage testing, validation and integration, and proto-typing of the technology, especially in the development of

the autonomous behaviors, sensing pipelines, and coordinated robotic operations. Towards these multiple tools are used with in Persephone, where some key elements of the simulation infrastructure include:

- **Gazebo-based Simulator:** Developed within the WP8, Task 8.2, the simulator serves as a modular testbed for autonomy, mapping and drilling tasks (details in D8.2), see Figure 5 and Figure 6. This simulator integrates URDF robot models developed within Persphone, ROS compatible sensor emulators, developed autonomy stack like STAGE planner (Task 4.1), traversability maps (Task 4.3), semantic navigation packages, etc, and the digital mining environments. These digital mining environments have been field collected using LiDAR and camera data from Gracian Magnesite and KGHM mines, which then have been converted into high-resolution 3D mesh and point cloud environments. These simulation modules form a special backbone for testing exploration and deployment behaviors in the simulation.

Figure 5: Gazebo simulation world created from the point cloud laser scan from the GM mine. The laser scan is converted into a mesh file and updated with a robot model.

Figure 6: A more realistic integration of the magnesite ore veins texture on the tunnel wall in the simulation world used for realistic visual feedback

- **Elyptica and Leapfrog (WP7):** Geo-model outputs are simulated and updated in parallel with the robotic missions, enabling a live digital twin for validation of real-time modelling and structural feedback.

3.3.2 Field facilities

Testing robotic solutions through field trials and real-world deployments is crucial for evaluating their robustness, scalability, the transferability of simulation results, and over all readiness for operational deployment. The following mine sites and partner labs have supported field and real world deployments:

- **Gracian Magnesite (GM)** – Abandoned underground mine (Greece) have hosted multiple mobility and sensing trials using Unitree robot with the

autonomy payload. The key evaluation include: i) Multispectral camera tests for ore detection (T2.4 and T6.1); ii) Navigation and mapping tests using Unitree robot (T4.1–T4.3), as seen in Figure 7, and VLM-based visual alignment testing (T 4.2).

Figure 7: Unitree robot with the navigation sensor suit at GM underground mine facility

- KGHM Mine (Poland)** – Active deep underground mine use case provided conditions for testing hole deviation monitoring (T2.2), and field calibration of ore characterization system (T6.2). Integration tests of the LTU were also conducted to integrate the LTU’s navigation autonomy sensor suit (WP4) with GSB multispectral camera (WP6), seen in Figure 8. Also, GSB’s Hyperspectral camera (WP6) was also successfully tested, see Figure 9. The outcome of this was collected from structural map from the LiDAR scans of the underground mine as well as also collect spectral ore data from the multi- and hyper- spectral cameras.

Figure 8: a) Multispectral camera with the 100 W halogen light set-up on the back of the Unitree robot integrated with the LTU navigation sensor suit, b) Covering the mine face with the multispectral camera

Figure 9: Stand-alone hyperspectral camera (Specim FX10e)+tripod+450W halogen light rig, b) Mine face image, c) Hyperspectral image of the mine face with ore concentration

- LTU Robotics Lab:** LTU has access to an underground tunnel that provides a few hundred meters of tunnels of different sizes, shapes, and terrains. This tunnel environment serves as a field lab used for testing preliminary autonomous behavior developments of the robot (WP4). As seen in the Figure 10, early deployment of the robot traversability algorithms were being tested. The tunnel lab provides a controlled yet realistic environment for validating the autonomy kit under representative underground conditions.

Figure 10: Early development on robot behaviour testing in scenarios with highly untraversable zones during completely autonomous navigation

- Epiroc test facility:** Some components of the development of Task 2.3 were tested in the Epiroc's laboratory facility at Orebro, Sweden. This facility provided a facility to test the long hole deviation monitoring system part of T2.3. This system was also further tested at the Nacka test mine, which provides an environment that closely resembles a real mine, with similar infrastructure, although it is not an active production site. The test

mine only has two levels, one at 40m and the second at 80m deep. This controlled environment allows for testing under realistic underground conditions without the constraints of ongoing mining operations.

Figure 11: Long hole drilling test in an underground mine recording the hole deviation data

3.4 Validation Activity Across Work Packages

This section summarizes the field experiments and simulation tests conducted during the first half of the PERSEPHONE project (up to M18), focusing on activities carried out under the technical work packages WP2, WP4, WP6, and WP7. During this period, majority of the time was consumed on the individual component development and testing followed by the beginning of the integration tasks across WPs. Thus, all the tasks in each WP have contributed critical validation activities toward the project's integrated mission scenarios. Validation has occurred across different environments:

- Simulation using Gazebo-based mining scenarios and custom robotic testbeds
- Laboratory setups for subsystem calibration, prototyping, and sensor benchmarking
- Field trials at real, abandoned and test mine environments

In WP2, T2.1 contributed with the blast simulation using FEM models, which demonstrated that collar initiation offers the most controlled energy distribution for rock preconditioning, informing downstream excavation planning in Mission Scenario 3. T2.2 validated a gyroscope-based hole deviation monitoring system during underground field trials at KGHM, achieving sub-2 cm deviation accuracy, thus supporting precise alignment for autonomous drilling. T2.3 focused on the

mechanical and software integration of the Stinger drilling robot, with successful deployment and drill-path execution tested in simulation. In T2.4, a comprehensive data model and sensor system was used to develop the capability to transform the raw sensor measurements to develop a useful geomodel, a key enabler for MS2 and MS4. T2.5 completed a series of geomechanical simulations, optimizing pillar layouts and integrating results into Elytica for structural risk modelling, directly supporting geomodel updates in MS4 and decision support in MS5.

In WP4, the STAGE planner was successfully validated in Gazebo environments (T4.1) derived from real mine scans, achieving >90% exploration coverage and robust local and global navigation switching, essential for MS1 and MS2. In addition, T4.1 also developed multi-machine coordination strategies to share their individual maps and sensor information, enabling successful task handover between robots. T4.2 advanced RGB-D and surface-normal-based alignment, with early integration of vision-language models (VLMs) under test for semantic scene understanding, supporting high-precision drill positioning in MS3. In T4.3, semantic and geometric traversability maps were developed and tested using a multi-layer fusion pipeline, enabling the robot to avoid high-risk zones during exploration. WP4.4 demonstrated reliable multi-agent mapping and localization through the FRAME framework and Zenoh-based mesh networking; graph merge success exceeded 90%, confirming readiness for MS1 and MS2 deployments. WP4.5 simulated the full autonomous drilling loop using behavior trees and the Stinger robot, with successful drill execution in 4 out of 5 preliminary test run, proving system stability and behavior control in lab environments.

From WP6, Task 6.1 confirmed the viability of real-time material characterization via LIBS and multispectral imaging; the system operated on-board the mobile robot, providing an integration activity between WP4 and WP6. The sensor data was successfully recorded with the time stamp and localization data from the navigation sensors into the autonomy stack. Task 6.2 advanced the logic for drill hole quality monitoring, incorporating MWD sensors and structuring outputs for geomodel input. In WP7, Tasks 7.1 and 7.3 validated the integration of sensor data into Elytica-based geo-models, enabling quasi-real-time updates of subsurface structures, while Tasks 7.2 and 7.4 initiated development of digital twin dashboards with active input from autonomy logs, drill status, and sensor data streams.

The table below summarizes the validation efforts conducted under each relevant WP, highlighting the technologies tested, current maturity (as of M18) of key subsystems developed (TRL levels), and alignment with PERSEPHONE's mission scenarios.

As summarized in the Table 1, all validation efforts contribute directly to the incremental maturity of PERSEPHONE's mission-driven architecture. Simulation environments allow for the repeated, low-risk testing, while field trials at underground facilities and mines enable real-world confirmation of subsystem performance. WP6 and WP7 act as critical bridges, connecting physical sensing and autonomy outputs to geomodeling, decision support, and digital twin

frameworks. Together, these validation efforts confirm progressive maturity, robust cross-WP integration, and readiness for large-scale demonstration under the upcoming WP9 tasks.

Table 1: Overview of the validation activities in WP2, WP4, WP6, and WP7

WP Task	Validation type	Achieved TRL (M18)	Mission Scenario(s)	Validation Highlight
WP2: Phase 1 - Technologies for Smart, Sustainable and Energy efficient Deposit Exploration and Extraction Systems				
T2.1- Rock preconditioning	Simulation (FEM)	TRL 4	MS3	Blast energy modelling optimized; collar-based initiation selected for reduced overbreak
T2.2- Hole deviation monitoring	Field test (Epiroc, KGHM mines)	TRL 5	MS3	Gyroscope sensor validated underground; deviation error within <2 cm tolerance.
T2.3 Drilling robot design	Simulation (Gazebo)+ Lab tests	TRL 4	MS3	“Stinger” prototype modelled; deployment scenarios tested for confined geometry navigation, with individual components test in lab experiments.
T2.4- Sensing technologies to develop geomodel	Simulation + Field (GM mine)	TRL 4	MS2, MS4	Sensor fusion pipeline validated; mineral classification with >85% accuracy, geomodel development from the raw sensor data.
T2.5- Extraction modelling	Simulations (Elytica + FEM)	TRL 4	MS4, MS5	Geo-mechanical models integrated with geo-model pipeline; pillar layout optimization run.
WP4: Phase 1 - Intelligence for Independent and Autonomous Deep Mine Drilling Exploration and Extraction Systems				
T4.1 Exploration planner	Simulation (Gazebo world)	TRL 4 -5	MS1, MS2	Graph-based planner tested in 3D mesh environment; 90% area coverage in simulated mine, multi-robot coordination strategies
T4.2- Drill face alignment, and navigation sensors	Simulation (Gazebo)+ Field data	TRL 3–4	MS2, MS3	Surface normals + RGB-D alignment successful; early VLM-based detection under testing, multi sensor fusion for navigation in harsh environments.
T4.3- Traversability assessment	Simulations (Gazebo)	TRL 4	MS1, MS2	Semantic and geometric risk layers are integrated into autonomy stack for safe planning.
T4.4- Multi-robot mapping	Simulations (Gazebo)	TRL 4	MS1, MS2	FRAME pipeline validated; decentralized mapping and graph merging successful.

T4.5- Drill Execution Workflow	Simulations (Gazebo)	TRL 4	MS3, MS5	Full FlexBE-based drill execution simulated; normal tensor voting used for safe placement of the stinger robot legs.
WP6 - Technologies for On-line Analytics Capabilities for Face Drilling and Extraction				
T6.1- Real-time material sensing	Simulation + Field Deployment	TRL 4	MS2, MS3	LIBS and multispectral sensing integrated with robot; tested with live feedback loop.
T6.2 Ore body modeling and drill hole quality tracking	Simulation and Lab tests	TRL 3 - 4	MS4, MS5	MWD sensor outputs structured for hole status monitoring and geo-model updates.
WP7 - Data-driven and dynamic Geo-modelling Synthesis for efficient extraction developments				
T7.1/7.3- Geomodel updates	Simulations	TRL 4	MS4	Sensor-derived features successfully linked to digital geo-models and 3D mine structures.
T7.2/7.4- Digital Twin & Support	Simulations	TRL 3 - 4	MS5	Dashboards for real-time twin updates under development; interfaces receiving live inputs.

3.5 Mission scenario status alignment

To ensure clarity and traceability in how technical developments from WP2, WP4, WP6, and WP7 contribute to PERSEPHONE's five Mission Scenarios (MS1–MS5), this section provides a scenario-wise summary of updates, integration readiness, and technology linkages. Each entry outlines: i) contributing work packages and tasks; ii) main components validated by M18; iii) relevant tests or prototypes completed; and iv) planned integration trajectory toward WP9.

MS1 – Autonomous mapping

- Contributing WPs: WP4 (T4.1, T4.3, T4.4), WP6 (T6.1)
- Validated Components:
 - STAGE planner (T4.1) for exploration and map building validated in GM simulation world.
 - Risk-aware semantic and geometric mapping (T4.3) integrated into navigation loop.
 - Multi-robot SLAM and graph merging via FRAME (T4.4) tested in simulation.
- Maturity: TRL 4–5 across modules; ready for deployment testing.
- Next Steps: Use in joint field missions; map sharing between robots to be tested under WP9.

MS2 – Advanced exploration

- Contributing WPs: WP2 (T2.4), WP4 (T4.1, T4.2, T4.3, T4.4), WP6 (T6.1, T6.2)
- Validated Components:
 - LIBS and multispectral sensor payloads integrated on mobile robots (T2.4, T6.1).
 - Visual servoing and drill-face alignment through RGB-D + surface normal estimation (T4.2).
 - VLM-based perception under test for semantic scene understanding.
- Maturity: TRL 4 for sensing, alignment, and TRL 3–4 for VLM integration.
- Next Steps: Field trial of combined perception-exploration flow, linking with geo-sensing logic in WP7.

MS3 – Autonomous production drilling

- Contributing WPs: WP2 (T2.1, T2.2, T2.3), WP4 (T4.2, T4.5), WP6 (T6.1, T6.2)
- Validated Components:
 - Drilling robot architecture (“Stinger”) modeled and simulated (T2.3).
 - Hole deviation sensing tested in real mine (T2.2), with <2 cm accuracy.
 - Drill plan execution behavior tree implemented (T4.5); alignment logic integrated.

- Maturity: TRL 5 for deviation sensing; TRL 4 for drilling autonomy loop.
- Next Steps: Demonstration of full drill alignment and execution loop; feedback to digital twin logic.

MS4 – Dynamic geomodelling

- Contributing WPs: WP2 (T2.5), WP6 (T6.2), WP7 (T7.1, T7.3)
- Validated Components:
 - Pillar layout modeling via FEM and Elytica (T2.5); structural updates fed into twin pipeline.
 - LIBS, MWD, and sensing integrated into the digital model for live updates (T6.2, T7.1).
- Maturity: TRL 4 for geo-model linkage; pipelines under early integration.
- Next Steps: Validate real-time update capacity during live mission runs in WP9.

MS5 – Decision support

- Contributing WPs: WP2 (T2.5), WP7 (T7.2, T7.4)
- Validated Components:
 - Digital twin dashboards and decision-support interfaces prototyped (T7.4).
 - Planning refinement algorithms from WP2.5 being linked with model outputs.
- Maturity: TRL 3–4; dashboard logic and input formatting under development
- Next Steps: Finalize interfaces between autonomy logs, sensor maps, and user-driven decision models.

4 Future plans

The work initiated in WP8 and related deliverable T8.1 to be continued in the upcoming task 9.1

All integration activities to be planned in detail in respective WP and to be followed up in the framework of WP9

5 Conclusions

The mission scenarios presented in this deliverable have proven to be a valuable tool for aligning the project's integration efforts. They have effectively facilitated cross-functional communication between different work packages and contributed to establishing a shared understanding among all project participants. Furthermore, the mission scenarios have served as a foundation for systematically monitoring the technology integration activities conducted during the first reporting period.

The report outlines the integration efforts through the use of a dedicated integration checklist, developed to provide a holistic overview of all contributions from WP2, WP4, WP6, and the upcoming WP7. This checklist has served as a practical management and coordination tool, allowing the project team to track Proof of Concept (PoC) achievements, monitor alignment with the project's specific objectives and novelties, and assess progress toward the PERSEPHONE vision. It has also supported the identification of interdependence across WPs and enabled efficient synchronization of technical developments.

In the remaining half of the project duration, the integration and evaluation work will continue along this established path under Task 9.1 in WP9. Future efforts will build on the current progress, with detailed planning and follow-up activities embedded within each relevant work package to ensure continued alignment with the project's overall vision and objectives.

6 Annex

N/A